

Influence of Teacher-Student Relationship on Student Mathematics Achievement in High School in the USA: Mediating Roles of Students Perceptions of Mathematics

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Abstract:

The teachers-students' interaction is at the center of teaching in the classroom and is a major factor in teaching quality and improving student achievement. The nature and quality of teacher-students' interaction is the basis for understanding student engagement. This paper explored influence of teacher-student relationship on student mathematics achievement in high schools. This study used descriptive survey design. Simple random sampling technique was further applied to obtain 470 persons. The study sampled 216 respondents by using Yamane formula. The collected data was analyzed using descriptive statistics, correlation, and regression

analysis through the statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 21. Research data were obtained through questionnaires and documentation. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics and multiple regression. The results of the findings indicated that the teacher-student relationship was more correlated with student mathematics achievement in High school ($r = 0.818$; $p = 0.000$). Multiple linear regression analysis showed that teacher-student relationship contributed to 44.5% of variation on the performance, hence plays a vital role in student mathematics achievement in high school. Additionally, it was further inferred that teacher-student relationship positive attitudes toward student mathematics achievement. The study recommended that students in high school should build positive student-teacher relationship with their teachers by engaging actively in classroom activities, showing respect to the Mathematics teacher and also try as much as possible to communicate consistently with the Mathematics teacher. Besides, Mathematics teachers should be encouraged to improve on their personal relationship with their students for this will enhance the academic performance of the students.

Keywords: *Teacher-student relationship, Mathematics achievement and student' perception.*

Introduction

Mathematics is the science that deals with the application of the cognitive domain and making computation. Though mathematics is seen as abstract, it is useful in a variety of industries, including design, software engineering, engineering, development, woodworking, and many more. (Lin et al,2020). The techniques and skills developed from mathematics have been

identified as essential not only for academic achievement but also for effective functioning in everyday life. Learners' life experiences have a significant impact on how well they succeed in arithmetic (Donohue, 2021). Learners' arithmetic performance has been a key source of concern for both the public and private education sectors. Scholars have succeeded in finding a variety of variables that greatly affect

learners' results, notably in arithmetic, over the last three decades. Various contributing variables such as the instructor-learner connection, self-efficacy, learners' perceptions of arithmetic, cooperative learning methods, and others, according to the researchers, have a substantial influence on mathematics achievement.

The instructor-learner connection had shown to have a negative influence on mathematics achievement in multiple research investigations (Park & Kim, 2006). According to research, the relationship between instructors and learners has a major impact on the arithmetic achievement of learners. If teachers want to create a great learning environment, they must first build a favourable relationship with their learners. If a kid sees their teacher as a "friend," they are more likely to get higher results. Many learners assume that their poor arithmetic performance is due to a lack of chemistry between teachers and learners. Teachers usually approach learners who have high-capacity levels and who are enthusiastic about the subject. Low-capacity learners are negatively impacted by this separation. Again, arithmetic is seen as a tough subject, and a healthy connection between instructor and learner can go a long way toward learners' achievement (Ferguson, 2001).

Vygotsky (1978) insisted that interaction and cooperation with others, such as that which occurs between teachers and peers, can stimulate learners' cognitive development. Namely, with the guidance of more competent individuals such as teachers, learners can internalize a certain function as a new ability (Kozulin, 2003). Therefore, learning does not occur through one-way lecturing; rather, learning occurs through reciprocal interactions within learning environments. This indicates that a student's response to a teacher's guidance is a critical factor for their learning, and that student beliefs can influence their responses to their teacher's guidance and produce different results for each teacher-student interaction. Reeve (2009) stressed the importance of reciprocal relationships between teachers and students, particularly with regards to student motivation.

Studies have demonstrated that the connection that exist between teachers and students assumes a significant part in the students' mathematics achievement (Hughes & Kwok, 2007). If teachers need to cultivate a good learning environment, a positive relationship with their students is the key. A student is bound to accomplish better outcomes if they see their teachers as a "buddy" (Pianta, 1999). Many students believe that an absence of affinity among teachers and students shows their poor performance in mathematics. Normally, teachers typically come nearer to students with high-capacity levels, who end up being positive about the subject. This separation unfavorably influences low-capacity students. Murray-Hannula (2007) stated that mathematics is seen to be a troublesome subject and accordingly, a good relationship among teachers and students goes far to help improve student achievement.

Most studies will first assume that teacher-student relationships can predict academic achievement and thus measure the impact of this relationship on achievement. For example, some scholars have found that teacher-student conflicts affect children's academic achievement (Kaasila et al, 2001). In fact, these investigations and studies on the role of teacher-student relationship in academic achievement are mostly based on self-determination theory. The theory holds that teacher-student interaction and student participation work together to determine their academic achievement. On this basis, basic needs theory was derived (Zelmeman et al., 2002). They believe that students have three kinds of psychological needs that are crucial for the participation of teachers, which are autonomy, ability development and relatedness. These needs also affect the quality of students' interpersonal relationships.

Students' mathematical achievement scores have been widely used as indicators of students' academic performance in school. However, there is much debate as to which factors influence students' mathematical achievement and how they vary across countries. Previous studies have provided empirical evidence for the effects of student- and school-level factors on U.S. students' mathematical achievement.

However, most studies have examined only one or some of these characteristics as predictors of mathematical achievement, but not yet explored various student and teacher characteristics simultaneously. Thus, based on the existing theoretical and empirical research, this study utilizes a conceptual framework that student academic outcome (i.e., mathematical achievement in this study) is explained by various student- and school-level factors. It is against that background that the study attempted to assess the influence of teacher-student relationship on student mathematics achievement in high schools: mediating roles of students' perceptions of mathematics.

Problem Statement

The teacher-student relationship is usually regarded as one of the most important interpersonal relationships in the classroom context. Especially, the teacher-student relationship is a dyadic social process that comprises ongoing interactions between teachers and students in classrooms (Ryan, 2001). Teachers and students go through a process of meeting one another, exchanging information, and adjusting and developing expectations, so the teacher-student relationship was regarded as teachers' and students' interactions over time, affect each other and aggregate perceptions of one another (Tella, 2008). In the last 20 years, the effect of the teacher-student relationship on students' academic performance has been supported by relevant theoretical and empirical studies (Xu & Qi., 2019).

Scholars and education stakeholders have expressed concern about learners' poor performance in mathematics and this terrible arithmetic performance levels have had a negative impact on the country's science and technology (Chand et al., 2021). As a result of this abysmal performance, a great deal of research had been done on some factors that influence students' mathematics achievements (Assiyari, 2004). Following a thorough study of the literature, mathematics achievement can be predicted by factors such as teacher-student relationship, students' self-efficacy, students'

perception of mathematics and cooperative learning strategies with varying results and conclusions (Callaman & Itaas, 2020).

The current problem is that, out of the studies reviewed, majority of these factors were predicting mathematics achievement disjointly and the few ones that combined two or more factors in predicting mathematics achievement were looking into only the direct influence. The ability to combine two or more of such variables and their direct and indirect influence on mathematics achievement has not been adequately studied. In order to bridge this gap, the researcher intended to investigate the mediating roles of students' perception of mathematics on the relationship between teacher-student relationship and students' mathematics achievement.

This study sought to achieve the following research hypothesis:

H₀₁: There is no significance influence between teacher-student relationship and student mathematics achievement in high schools.

Methodology

This study aimed to reveal teacher-student interactions that construct students' mathematical understanding. Researchers appreciate and observe, select, and interpret teacher-student experiences in mathematics learning in the classroom. Observation aims to gain a deep understanding of teacher-student interactions in mathematics learning. This research was conducted by observing directly the process of learning mathematics in the classroom to see teacher-student interactions. This study evaluated influence between teacher-student relationship and student mathematics achievement in high schools.

The researcher used descriptive research survey design in building up this project work the choice of this research design was considered appropriate because of its advantages of identifying attributes of a large population from a group of individuals. The design was suitable for the study as the study sought influence

between teacher-student relationship and student mathematics achievement in high schools.

Population of a study is a group of persons or aggregate items; things the researcher is interested in getting information on the study factors influencing the attitude of students towards the study of mathematics in US in state of Mississippi. It is smaller than most of the U.S. states and is bounded on the north by Tennessee, on the east by Alabama, on the south by Louisiana and the Gulf of Mexico, and on the west by Louisiana and Arkansas. This study was delimited in Coahoma County. Data was collected in the Clarksdale High School. (Mississippi Report Card, 2022). The population of this study was 464 students and 6 Mathematics teachers from Clarksdale High School. Thus, the total population was 470 persons.

In addition, the study used the following formula proposed by using Yamane (1973) to determine the sample size because that is too large waste scarce resources and could expose more participants than necessary to any related risk. Thus, the study used Yamane formula to calculate a sample size because it is the most appropriate for this study.

Using Yamane formulae

$$n = \frac{N}{1+(N)(e^2)} \quad (1)$$

Where:

n = sample size

N = the population size

e = the acceptable sampling error (5%) at 95% confidence level

Thus;

$$n = 470 / (1+(470) (0.05)^2)$$

$$n=216.09=216 \text{ respondents}$$

In this study the researcher used questionnaires, and documentary review. Closed-ended

questions were used where the answers were divided into categories such discrete, distinct and relatively few in number. It is easier for respondents to answer because they had only to choose categories. In that way a chance for irrelevant answers is limited to the minimum, because appropriate answer categories were provided. The main respondents were being teachers that were given the questionnaire as they were enough time to respond to the questions based on research hypothesis. Questionnaires were given to Mathematics teachers and principals and students.

The questionnaire used as the research instrument was subjected to face its validation. This research instrument (questionnaire) adopted was adequately checked and validated by the supervisor his contributions and corrections were included into the final draft of the research instrument used.

Findings and Discussion

Findings

In this study the research sampled 216 respondents from Clarksdale High School. The data collected from the respondents were analyzed in tabular form with simple percentage for easy understanding. A total of 210 questionnaires of students were distributed and only 174 questionnaires were returned back. Besides, all 6 mathematics teachers responded the questionnaire.

Descriptive Statistics of Teacher-Student Relationship on Student Mathematics Achievement

In this research the study attempted to determine the f Influence of teacher-student relationship on student mathematics achievement. The respondents were asked to rate the statements by indicating the extent to which they apply to their organization in 5-point Likert scale as shown on: 5. Strongly Agree (SA), 4Agree(A), 3. Neutral (N), 2. Disagree (D) and 1. Strongly Disagree (SD). Besides, the mean and deviation were used for interpretation of the findings where mean (M) is the average of group

of scores and it is sensitive to extreme score when the population samples are small. Moreover, the standard deviation (SD) was also

used to measure the variability in those statistics as it shows how much variation is there from the average (mean).

Table 1. Teacher-Student Relationship on Student Mathematics Achievement

Statements	Mean	Std Dev
Teacher-student interaction consists of the teacher’s delivering material and students paying attention	4.2	0.69
The delivery of material by the teacher is influenced by the mastery of the material and skills in selecting the right strategy to teach Mathematics	4.4	0.78
The task of the math teacher is to carry out the mathematics learning process, and foster a sense of pleasure and love for mathematics	3.7	0.75
Teachers’ mathematical knowledge made statistically significant changes in their lesson design, their mathematical agenda, and the classroom climate	3.9	0.96
To convey the material the teacher uses a lecture strategy, to increase student interest and motivation.	4.3	0.95
The teacher uses games to foster motivation and attract students’ attention in case students focus and work on the questions they receive	3.5	0.52
Teachers are advised to use appropriate learning strategies to meet the needs of students in delivering material.	4.1	0.76

Source: Field research, 2023

As shown in Table 1, the results relate to the seven statements assessing the influence of Teacher-student relationship on student mathematics achievement in high school in Coahoma County in Clarksdale High School. The results show that for the first statement, the majority of respondents strongly agreed that Teacher-student interaction consists of the teachers delivering material and students paying attention, with a mean value of 4.2, and a high positive correlation standard deviation of 0.69. The second statement asked respondents whether the delivery of material by the teacher is influenced by the mastery of the material and skills in selecting the right strategy to teach Mathematics. The results showed that the majority of respondents strongly agreed with this statement (M=4.4, SD=0.78). For the third statement, the task of the math teacher is to carry out the mathematics learning process, and foster a sense of pleasure and love for mathematics, the majority of respondents agreed with this statement, with a mean of 3.7 and a very positive and high standard deviation correlation of 0.75. The fourth statement asked whether the Teachers’ mathematical knowledge made statistically significant changes in their lesson design, their mathematical agenda, and the

classroom climate. Respondents strongly agreed with this statement, with an average mean of 3.9 and a very strong positive standard correlation of 0.96. The next item was whether to convey the material the teacher uses a lecture strategy, to increase student interest and motivation. The majority of them strongly agreed that statement with a mean of 4.3 and a very high positive standard deviation of 0.95. The next item respondents were asked whether the teacher uses games to foster motivation and attract students’ attention in case students focus and work on the questions they receive, the respondents agreed that statement (M=3.5, SD=0.52). On the last statement respondents were asked teachers are advised to use appropriate learning strategies to meet the needs of students in delivering material, the majority of respondents strongly agreed and agreed that statement with a mean score of 4.1 and positive correlation standard deviation of 0.76. From the results, it implies that the majority of respondents strongly agreed and agreed that all of the above are key elements of teacher-student relationship and student mathematics achievement.

Correlation Analysis

The findings of the correlations between the independent variables and the dependent

variables are summarized and presented in Table 3.

Table 2. Correlation Between Variables

		Teacher-student relationship	Student Mathematics achievement
Teacher-student relationship	Pearson Correlation	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)		
	N	174	
Student Mathematics achievement	Pearson Correlation	.818**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	174	174

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

According to the findings reported in Table 2, the Pearson correlation analysis showed that teacher-student relationship ($r=0.818$, $p=0.000$) is positively and significantly related to student Mathematics achievement in high school. The correlation was deemed to be statistically significant since the p-value was less than 5%. The findings therefore showed that there is a positive and statistically significant relationship between teacher-student relationship and student Mathematics achievement in high school.

The data of this study confirms the hypothesis and finds that teacher-student relationship is positively correlated with students' mathematics achievement. Students with higher level of teacher-student relationship are more likely to

have higher academic achievement. This study is consistent with the research findings of Birch (1997) and Wang (2002), which once again confirmed the positive role of teacher-student relationship in individual learning, especially in school education.

Multiple Regression

A multiple regression analysis was performed in this section to identify the predictor and its contribution towards the criterion. It aims to determine the prediction of a single dependent variable from a group of independent variables. The multiple regression analysis was performed with all the assumptions complied with. The results of the multiple regression are presented in Table 3 to Table 5.

Table 3. Multiple Correlation of Independent Variables with Dependent Variable

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.670 ^a	.450	.445	.69075

a. Predictors: (Constant), Teacher-student relationship

The table 3 below shows the quantity of variance that is explained by the predictor variables. The first statistic, R is the multiple correlation coefficient between all the predictor variables and dependent variable. In is model, the value is .670^a, which indicates that there is a great deal of variance shared by the independent variables and dependent variables. The next value, R Square, is simply the squared value of R. This is frequently

used to describe the goodness of fit or the amount variance explained by a given set of predictor variables and its value is 44% of the variance in the dependent variable is explained by independent variables in the model.

The table above indicated standard regression which provides the influence of individual predictor variable. That variable is teacher-

student relationship. The table shows the output analysis and whether there is a statistically significant difference group mean. As seen, it, the significance value is 0.001 and the mean is

0.684. Therefore, there is a statistically significant difference in the mean length of model.

Table 4. Significance of Independent Variables

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	182.035	4	45.509	66.538	.000 ^b
	Residual	77.287	113	.684		
	Total	259.322	117			
a. Dependent Variable: Student Mathematics achievement						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Teacher-student relationship						

Table 5. Regression Coefficients and Significance of the Independent Variable

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.479	.313		4.732	.000
	Students attitude	-.221	.038	-.371	-5.845	.000
a. Dependent Variable: Student Mathematics achievement						

Information presented in Table 5 evidenced that $Y=1.479 -0.221 X_1 ++\epsilon$ Where $y=$ Student Mathematics achievement. The regression output above shows that teacher-student relationship variable is statistically equal to 0.000. This shows the regression of independent variable is associated with Student Mathematics achievement. Multiple analysis regression result above indicates the influence of independent variables based on the regression coefficient. The unstandardized Coefficients is 1.479 when is constant and at the same time the Std. Error is 0.313 when they are associated with coefficients. The significant predictor out of four independent variables are positively related to the criterion in the regression, as shown in Table 5.

Discussion

The results of this study are forms of teacher-student interaction in mathematics learning that can help students build and improve mathematical understanding. From the findings, the study found that teacher-student relationship influence student Mathematics achievement when their interaction consists of the teachers

delivering material and students paying attention, when the delivery of material by the teacher is influenced by the mastery of the material and skills in selecting the right strategy to teach Mathematics, when the task of the math teacher is to carry out the mathematics learning process, and foster a sense of pleasure and love for mathematics, when the teachers' mathematical knowledge made statistically significant changes in their lesson design, their mathematical agenda, and the classroom climate, when to convey the material the teacher uses a lecture strategy, to increase student interest and motivation, when the teacher uses games to foster motivation and attract students' attention in case students focus and work on the questions they receive and finally when teachers are advised to use appropriate learning strategies to meet the needs of students in delivering material.

Besides, the Pearson correlation analysis showed that teacher-student relationship ($r=0.818$, $p=0.000$) is positively and significantly related to student Mathematics achievement in high school. The correlation was deemed to be statistically significant since the p-value was less than 5%. The findings therefore showed that there is a positive and statistically significant

relationship between teacher-student relationship and student Mathematics achievement in high school.

These findings are relevant with McCarthy et al (2016) who stated that Teacher-students' interaction needs to be created in learning, especially in mathematics. Students need attention, stimulation, and guidance in learning mathematics. However, there are still many teachers who have not implemented positive teacher-student interactions. The results of interviews with several mathematics teachers said that the teacher had not interacted well with students. There are still teachers who only deliver material, give assignments then leave students and return to the office, then discuss questions, and give homework. According to students, mathematics teachers tend to be grumpy and angry when there are students who have not been able to work on the questions. This creates students afraid to ask questions and interact with the teacher. Apart from this, there are still many teachers who do not know how and what interactions teachers-students need to be carried out in learning to build a conducive learning atmosphere and a good understanding of mathematics.

To sum it up, students who are perceived to have confidence in themselves are capable of excelling in the mathematics subject as suggested and tested by many researchers. Callaman and Itaas (2020) reported that academic self-efficacy is connected with academic achievement in the mathematics examination. The belief that students develop about their academic capabilities helps to determine what they do with the knowledge and skills they possess which eventually determines their academic achievement.

Conclusion and Recommendations

From the findings, the study concluded teacher-student relationship can significantly affect mathematical achievement, and has a positive predictive influence, and its impact on mathematical achievement is greater than teacher-student relationship. This study is

consistent with the research findings of Birch (1997) and Wang (2002), which once again confirmed the positive role of teacher-student relationship in individual learning, especially in school education.

Therefore, the researcher can conclude by saying that the research hypotheses including: "H₀₁: There is no significance influence between teacher-student relationship and student mathematics achievement in high schools"; all were tested; verified and then they are confirmed referring to the statistical (regression analysis) findings and then according to the research, the correlation of 0.818 (81.8%) categorized as positive and very high correlation; this leads to confirm that there is significant influence between teacher-student relationship and student mathematics achievement

Based on the findings, it can be recommended that to implementing activities that are full of interactions between teachers and students in high schools should build positive student-teacher relationship with their teachers by engaging actively in classroom activities, showing respect to the Mathematics teacher and also try as much as possible to communicate consistently with the Mathematics teacher. Mathematics teachers should be encouraged to improve on their personal relationship with their students for this will enhance the academic performance of the students. They should also bring their wealth of experience in teaching of Mathematics to the level of students' aptitude to make personal relationships of students with their teachers more interesting so as to arouse the interest of the students to academic excellence.

References

- Asiyai, R. (2004). Students' perception of the condition of their classroom physical learning environment and its impact on their learning motivation. *College Student Journal*, 48(4), 716-726.
- Callaman, R. A., & Itaas, E. C. (2020). Students' mathematics achievement in Mindanao context: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Research and Advances in Mathematics Education*, 5(2), 148-159.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.23917/jramathedu.v5i2.10282>

Chand, S., Chaudhary, K., Prasad, A., & Chand, V. (2021). Perceived causes of students' poor performance in mathematics: A case study at Ba and Tavua secondary schools. *Frontiers in Applied Mathematics and Statistics*, 7, 614408. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fams.2021.614408>

Donohue, D. (2021). Culture, cognition, and college: How do cultural values and theories of intelligence predict students' intrinsic value for learning? *Journal of Culture and Values in Education*, 4(1), 1–14. <http://dx.doi.org/10.46303/jcve.2020.3>

Hannula, M. S. (2007). *The effect of achievement, gender and classroom contexts on upper secondary students' mathematical beliefs*. Lyon France.

Hair, J. F., Bush, R. P., & Ortinau, D. J. (2009). *Marketing research: Within a changing information environment?* McGraw-Hill Higher Education.

Hughes, M. F. (2017). Similar students-dissimilar opportunities for success: High- and low achieving elementary schools in rural, high-poverty areas of West Virginia. *Journal of Research in Rural Education*, 15(1), 47-58.

Ferguson, M. R. (2001). Teaching and learning: Inside the Korean culture. *International Education*, 10(2), 16–23. http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-06127-6_4

Lin, W., Yin, H., Han, J., & Han, J. (2020). Teacher–student interaction and chinese students' mathematics learning outcomes: The mediation of mathematics achievement emotions. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(13), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17134742>

Kaasila, R. T., Hannula, M. S., Laine, A., & Pehkonen, E. (2006). Facilitators for change of elementary teacher student's view of mathematics. In Proceedings of the 30th Conference of the *International Group for the Psychology of Mathematics Education* (pp. 385-392).

Kozulin, A. (2003). Psychological tools and mediated learning. In: A. Kozulin, B. Gindis, V. Ageyev, & S. Miller (Eds.), *Vygotsky's educational theory in cultural context* (pp. 15–38). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

Park, Y. S., & Kim, U. (2006). Family, parent-child relationship, and academic achievement in Korea. In U. Kim, K. S. Yang, & K. K. Hwang, (Eds.), *Indigenous and Cultural Psychology* (pp. 421–443). Springer.

Pianta, R. C. (1999). *Enhancing relationships between children and teachers*. American Psychological Association.

Reeve, J. (2009). Why teachers adopt a controlling motivating style toward students and how they can become more autonomy supportive. *Educational Psychologist*, 44(3), 159–175.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/00461520903028990>

Ryan, R.M., & Patrick, H. (2001). The classroom social environment and changes in adolescents' motivation and engagement during middle school. *American Educational Research Journal*, 38, 437-460.

<https://doi.org/10.3102/00028312038002437>

Tella, A. (2008). Teacher variables as predictors of academic achievement of primary school pupils' mathematics. *International Electronic Journal of Elementary Education*, 1(1), 16-33

Vygotsky, L. (1978). Interaction between development and learning. In M. Gauvain & M. Cole (Eds.), *Readings on the development of children* (2nd ed., pp. 79–91). W. H. Freeman and Company.

Xu, Z. Z., & Qi, C. (2019). The relationship between teacher-student relationship and academic achievement: The mediating role of self-efficacy. *EURASIA Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 15(10),67-89. <http://dx.doi.org/10.29333/ejmste/105610>